

सत्यमेव जयते

ISSN : 2320-1460

NATIONAL JOURNAL OF EXTENSIVE EDUCATION AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

Volume II Issue - I
Jan.-March 2014

Government College of Education,
Institute for Advanced Studies in
Education, Aurangabad (M.S.)

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The Issues and Challenges in Distance Education

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Introduction :

There was no issue when man was not created on the earth. This creation of God brought issues related to its existence and challenges to other living and non-living beings. This is also true in case of any other from including Distance Education, whose started has lead to many issues and challenges. Hence, it is essential to know history of Distance Education. The Correspondence Programmes of Delhi University started in 1962 is usually considered as the beginning of distance education in Indian higher education. The establishments of first Open University in 1982 at Hyderabad and National Open University at Delhi in 1985 were the landmarks in the growth of distance education or open distance learning in India. Today, it is a huge system with 14 Open Universities and around 200 institutions offering distance programmes in diverse areas with an estimated enrolment of around 40 lakh students. This is a huge number and the entire process of imparting education and management of learning is a complex activity. In the western world in Wedemeyer in 1960s broke from the concept of correspondence study and focused instead on independent study. Peters (mid 1960s) analysed the structure of distance education and noted the possibility of adopting industrial production techniques such as a division of labour, mass production, and organization to realize economies of scale and reduce unit costs. In 1973 Moore introduced the theory of independent study by giving distance education as a function of 'dialogue' and 'individualisation' with learner autonomy.

The authors are highly indebted to Prof. V. S. Prasad whose ideas (presented in Prof. G. Rame Reddy Memorial Lecture, in IDEA 2013 conference held at MANUU) have been used extensively used in writing this paper.

The author would like to co-relate his knowledge of distance education with the decent of Quran on humanity fourteen centuries ago. It is author's perception that Hazrat Muhammed (PBUH), The Messenger of Allah was revealed the Quran Shareef in Distance Mode by the Almighty Allah, the teacher, the creator, the omnipotent and omnipresent. The Holy Quran is a best example of a self learning material (SLM), where the learner is addressed at various places, given concrete example from his/her life. The learner is presented with promises of reward and punishments for his good or bad deeds and his sanctity is checked every now and then with regard to his faith. The present day course materials make use of various important characteristics of SLM, which are present in the holy book. There may be many more characteristics which are yet to discovered by distance educators.

Issues Related to Theory and Practice of Distance Education

- The distance education gives a greatest possible control over the time, place and pace of education of a learner; however, it is not without problems. Loss of student motivation due to the lack of face-to-face contact with teachers and peers, potentially prohibitive start up costs, and lack of faculty support are all some of concerns to the successful distance learning.
- The issues of distance education include the quality of instruction, hidden costs, misuse of technology, research, evaluation and the attitudes of instructors, students, and administrators. Each one of these has an effect on the overall quality of distance learning as a product. In many ways, each of these issues relates to the others.

The Open Distance Learning (ODL) is a way of thinking and a way of doing. The essential

theoretical elements of Distance Education which encounter different issues include:

An effective instrument for democratisation of education :

Access to all and learner managing their own learning are two essential elements of democratisation of learning. The open admission policies are based on the assumption that it is exit standards, not the entry standards that matter. Like citizen is the centre of democratic polity, the learner is the centre of democratic education system (Prasad, 2012). How far present day institutions working to fulfil important goal is an issue that comes to our mind?

A means for social justice :

The flexibility of study enables the learners to manage their study, learn from geographic location that otherwise would be excluded; supports the inclusion of women; permits participation of groups and communities otherwise shut out by costs. This is more an inclusive form of education and hence social justice is ensured. The distance education has lot of social responsibility towards, backward, downtrodden and remotely located population. The issue is whether the social justice motto is fulfilled in market driven world of institutions.

Technology mediated form of education :

Distance education is a delivery of teaching and learning by a variety of mediating processes to those who are separated by time and space from those who are teaching. Whether Distance Education Institutions (DEIs) use technology for technology per se or to bridge the gap between teachers and taught?

Quality imperatives :

The Quality of learning materials, student support services, student evaluation and administrative services are critical to the effectiveness of distance education. In the present era quality is meant for public scrutiny and how many institutes are ready for this?

Teacher as a facilitator :

Teachers in ODL are facilitators, than traditional instructors. This paradigm shift is not visible at study centre, multi-media for of teaching-learning is not being fully used by academic counsellor.

The institution as promoter ;

It is observed that in conventional education teacher teaches, where as in distance education, institution teaches. Hence, they should have good logistics along with good learning materials and good students support services. Whether present day institutions are fulfilling this is a thing to be pondered.

The Practice of Distance Education :

Indian Distance Education system can be described "as one system, many models". There is a great variation in the practices of the system. The practices are exemplified as:

Large enrolment :

Delhi University started correspondence programme with an enrolment of 1112 students. Now, we have ODL institutions like Open Universities and Distance education centres with hundreds of thousands of enrolment in each institution. The MANUU a dual mode university, working in minority language medium claims of having 1.57 lakh students in its prospectus that are spread across the nation (MANUU, 2014). Such a wider group has different requirements in the form of courses, skills, mediums, support system and whether our distance institutes are gearing to meet these demands?

Diversification of programmes :

Initially ODL institutions started with liberal arts programmes, with assumption that ODL is appropriate for education of liberal arts only. Now, the ODL system is offering all types of programmes in Science, Technology, Education, Management, Health Science, Agriculture, Information Technology, Arts, and Culture. During the last fifty years of ODL, the pendulum of programme offerings moved from one extreme of restricting only to Arts programmes to another extreme of offering any programmes. There are large number of disciplines which are coming up every day and bringing new challenges for the universities to face.

Active role by private sector :

The private sector, particularly major players in Industry are trying to use ODL for development of human resources, particularly in professional and vocational fields. Many private players are offering education and training programmes through ODL. Giving tailor made programmes to suite private sector is a challenge for distance education institutes.

Commercialisation as a drive for expansion :

The expansion and diversification of ODL is driven more by profit motives of private sector or resource mobilisation drive of public sector ODL institutions. These commercial motives are influencing institutional decisions about learning materials, support services, evaluation systems and administrative arrangements.

Use of technology :

The correspondence institutes started with use of print materials for delivery of programmes with not much student support services. Over the years multimedia in various forms is being used by many ODL institutions. The interactive media, online programmes bring new ICT and need the institutes to develop the infrastructure on the one hand makes the government to strengthen programmes like National Mission on Education through ICT (NMEICT); National Knowledge Network (NKN); National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL) and many other such programmes. The COL, CEMCA, IGNOU are also taking many initiatives for technology use in ODL in India and this requires all the ODL institutes to work for the same.

Quality assurance systems :

There is a great variation in quality assurance policies, systems and practices followed by ODL institutions in India. At one end of the spectrum we have IGNOU, some state Open Universities and some ODL institutions, which do have quality assurance practices like good study materials, student support services, technology infrastructure etc. At the other end of the spectrum, many institutions are offering sub-standard ODL programmes with large enrolment by franchising delivery. There is a need for establishing some quality guidelines to monitor the system.

Regulatory framework for ODL :

After the merger of Distance Education Council (DEC) with the University Grants Commission (UGC), there appears to be a strong regulatory framework emerging. This can help in regulating standards in professional, technical and vocational programmes.

The Issues which are still pending

The critical examination of ODL practices shows some issues in distance education, which are still pending:

Distortion in the goals of ODL :

The profit making or resource generation orientations of some of ODL institutions results in

compromises with the social goals of the system. It is paradoxical to use the system meant for socially disadvantaged for generating resources.

Constraints on openness of ODL practices :

The products of ODL from the open admission stream are facing innumerable difficulties in further admissions to programmes in conventional system and in employment too. To cite an example, the degree holders who get their degree after passing Eligibility Test (without having XIIth or any formal education till secondary level), find it difficult to get jobs and even sometimes admissions in higher education after graduating from distance mode.

Limited use of interactive technology :

Interaction is the essence of education. The ODL in India is not able to effectively use interactive technologies in its teaching-learning activities. The challenge of the day is to use interactive software such as social media, blogs, wikis, and podcasts.

Lack of professionalism in management of ODL :

The governance system of most of ODL institutions lack professionalism in their operations. The simple expectations of ODL learners are to receive the materials on time and examinations to be conducted as per schedule. Even these expectations are not fulfilled by many ODL institutions. The systems are becoming huge and adequate structures are not created to attend to all the needs of learners. The student support services are to be professionally managed.

Ambiguity on the teachers role in ODL :

Teacher is equally important in ODL as that of in a conventional system. May be teachers' job in ODL is more complex and more difficult because of use of multiple technologies for teaching-learning purposes. There is a constant debate in ODL circles about the roles, responsibilities and relationships with others in the system. The teacher identity is not satisfactory addressed in ODL system.

Globalisation of Education and Cross-Cultural Aspects :

The present era is marked with globalised world, so also globalisation in education is imperative. Those groups which keep themselves away from the process of globalisation are not getting impact

of other cultures and development is also hampered. Distance Education is the best way to help in the globalised context.

Professional Development and Faculty Support in Distance Education :

In the Professional Development (PD) of staff in distance education, it is paramount to establish an understanding of the lived experiences of distance learner. 'Walk in my shoes' is an adage that needs to be a regular focus of staff development (academic, general, managerial, and governmental). The efforts of STRIDE are praise worthy in case of Distance Education institutes for professional development of faculty. Establishment of PD cell by each university to meet local demands is a challenge.

Innovations and Change in Distance Education

In terms of ensuring equity in distance education in terms of innovation and change, what budgetary provisions have been made by the institutions is also an important issue in distance education. Equity, access and participation issues need to be at forefront of any decision-making surrounding innovation and change.

Learner Support Services in Distance Education :

Learner support services are often overlooked aspects of equity issue in distance education. Lack of learner support services is a major challenge experienced by distance learners leading to withdrawals and non-completions.

Distance Education – Costs and Benefits :

Costs and benefits of distance education are often reported with a positive spin from the perspective of distance education institutes. Are there cost benefits only for the universities or it is meant for the learners too, as there is a paradigm shift from print-based technologies to electronic technologies resulting in benefit of time, access and finances to the learner. Mobile learning has led to anytime, anywhere learning with cut in paper cost and increased portability.

Distance Education Management and Organisation :

The management and organisation of distance education is an area not as frequently researched

as other areas of distance education. There is much to be explored in relation to this.

ICT in Distance Education :

In some sense this is related to distance education costs, ICT may be selected in terms of cost-effectiveness for the institution. It is a general notion that many distance education courses require ICT mediated technologies, skills and technical support that certain students might not have. This warrants lot of reflection on use of ICT in Distance Education.

The study on Technologies and Frameworks of Distance Learning in Iran: Needs and Challenges and the major issues by (Gharehbakloo & Reza, 2005) lead to findings that are related to teaching methodology (i.e. academic counselling), lack of attention to distance education in educational policies, inefficiency in distance learning management, inefficiency in curriculum, inequality for appreciating distance learning degrees, failure to create and enhance student's motivation, underdevelopment of the Internet in society, lack of skills in using the Internet.

Different problems and issues with distance education are lack of consistency in programme/policy implementation, problem of electricity, poor telecommunication facilities and lacks of access, poor postal system, poor economic situations and its effects on middle level manpower and poor ICT penetration (YUSUF, 2006). The quality of instruction, cost effectiveness, misuse of technology, role of the technicians and problems with equipment are some major problems and issues of distance education (Valentine, 2002).

When compared to traditional students, distance learners are more likely to have learning insecurities. Cost issues, disruption of family life, and lack of support from family and employers have effects on distance learners resulting in higher dropout rates when compared to traditional students.

Challenges in Distance Education :

Majority of population staying in rural areas and making them aware about use of ICT is a major challenge. Lack of infrastructure in terms of connectivity, availability of Internet, etc. is another

issue. The government is taking various measures to improve the communication systems and new technologies like 3G in the telecom space have already started to be implemented to make things better.

Although many universities and institutions working in distance education are working on platform for sharing their resources as Open Educational Resources (OER). The institutes find it difficult to share their material which is generated by them free of cost to all in global market. If the material is put on the OER then it increases social, academic audit by all those who are involved in the learning process. Thus, this brings lot of challenge for the host institutes.

India is a developing country which is part of the world that can easily be divided into the realm of the "haves" and the "have nots". There are many Indians who belong to second category. It is a major challenge for distance mode education to deal with the groups deprived of all facilities. Overcoming transactional distance between teacher and taught in distance education is possible by use of ICT, but making use of appropriate technology in India is a big challenge.

The important challenges that are being faced in developing countries are Cost, Electrical Power Grid Infrastructure, insufficient Communications, infrastructure in rural areas and Affordable Computers (Haines, 2006). The situations in India are also similar and these are also applicable in Indian conditions too. The use of Webcasts (Site-to-site, Closed broadcast, Open broadcast, Visual 2-way vs. visual 1-way, Audio 2-way vs. visual 1-way, Recommended practices); Video feeds/video links; Podcasts; Chats (A moderated chat, Video, Audio, Text, Voice-to-text); Online discussion forums (Broad discussions, Directed discussions, Recommended practices); Social Space (Information dissemination, Journals student reflections with faculty response, "Vlogging"); Wikis; Online quizzes etc present lot of challenge for both the teacher and taught in distance education mode is also an emerging challenge for DEIs in India.

The way forward :

The DEIs in India has made significant contributions in providing the space to space less in higher education. The system has acquired sufficient experience and acceptance to play an important role in future. The discussions on issues and challenges of the system are only to emphasise the need to overcome some of these limitations to reinvigorate the system to make more meaningful contributions.

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